

Modelling Potential-Induced Degradation: from Indoor Testing to Prediction of Long-Term Performance

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PID: a sneaky problem

PID depends on a **combination of causes**:

- **Climatic conditions** of installation site;
- Other **location-specific conditions**: salt-mist (coastal areas) or soiling could promote PID;
- **System design**: grounding, inverter choice, etc. ;
- **Module design**:
 - mounting solutions: frame vs rail bars;
 - bill of material (BOM) used in sandwich manufacturing

Potential-induced degradation (PID)

- PID in c-Si modules \Rightarrow rapid and severe power losses (infant failure)
- Widely studied:
 - Physical mechanism well understood [1]
 - Role of module materials [2, 5]
 - Predictive models, based on accelerated tests [3,4]

- Still needed improvement in modeling and prediction

String loss \sim -14%

* Data shared by an IPP

[1] V. Naumann et al., *SolMat* (2014)

[3] J. Hattendorf et al., *EUPVSEC* (2013)

[2] J. Berghold et al., *IEEE PVSC* (2014)

[4] S. Koch et al., *EUPVSEC* (2015)

[5] A. Virtuani et al., *PiP* (2019)

Model's outline

Model's outline

PID degradation as a function of:
temperature, humidity, applied voltage, time...

Indoor PID degradation at constant stress conditions (1)

- Accelerated PID tests at **different levels of stress**

- Stress factors:**
- Temperature T
 - Relative humidity RH
 - Voltage V

IEC TS 62804-1:2015

T / RH	75%	85%	95%
45°C		-1000 V	
60°C	-1000 V	-1000 V	-1000 V
75°C		-1000 V	
85°C		-200 V -400 V -600 V	

- P_{max} modeled as a function of stress factors

$$P(t) = P_{ini} \cdot \left(1 - A \cdot RH^B \cdot e^{-\frac{E_a}{\kappa \cdot T} \cdot t^2} \right)$$

E_a : activation energy of power loss

A, B : coefficients

κ : Boltzmann constant

Indoor PID degradation (2)

- Accelerated PID tests at **different levels of stress**

Stress factors:

- Temperature T
- Relative humidity RH
- Voltage V

IEC TS 62804-1:2015

T / RH	75%	85%	95%
45°C		-1000 V	
60°C	-1000 V	-1000 V	-1000 V
75°C		-1000 V	
85°C		-200 V -400 V -600 V	

- P_{max} modeled as a function of stress factors

$$P(t) = P_{ini} \cdot (1 - A \cdot V) \cdot RH^B \cdot e^{-\frac{E_a}{\kappa \cdot T} \cdot t^2}$$

Eq. for power degradation

➔ It is possible to simulate PID effect on an entire string of modules.

Model's outline

PID regeneration as a function of:
temperature, humidity, applied voltage, illumination,...

Power regeneration in the dark

β [-]	$E_a(\tau)$ [eV]
0.55	0.52

Definition: **Relative recovery** at time t

$$RR(t) := \frac{P(t) - P_{min}}{P_{ini} - P_{min}}$$

- Recovery in the dark strongly driven by temperature
- Fitting function [P. Lechner]

$$RR(t) = 1 - e^{-\left(\frac{t}{\tau(T)}\right)^\beta}$$

$$0 < \beta < 1$$

$$\tau(T) = \tau_{ref} \cdot e^{-\frac{E_a(\tau)}{\kappa} \cdot \left(\frac{1}{T} - \frac{1}{T_{ref}}\right)}$$

Indoor PID regeneration at constant conditions (1)

Power regeneration may occur during daytime

- Regeneration for negatively-biased samples (-1000 V) shown experimentally

Indoor PID regeneration at constant conditions (2)

- Regeneration for negatively-biased samples (-1000 V) shown experimentally

Power regeneration during daytime

- Regeneration for negatively-biased samples (−1000 V) shown experimentally
- Recovery capacity linked to damage level
- Model proposed fits well the results

$$RR(t) = (\lambda) \cdot \left(1 - e^{-\left(\frac{t}{\tau}\right)^\beta}\right)$$

Eq. for daytime regeneration

It is possible to simulate daytime regeneration.

PID: power regeneration

In the dark (night-time):

- Strong dependence on temperature;

With light exposure (daytime):

- module with negative applied bias can regenerate;
- load conditions (OC, MPP, negative bias) play a moderate role;
- level of illumination and temperature play a role which is not always reproducible (secondary order effect?)
- humidity plays a role;
- level of degradation plays a considerable role on regeneration

Model's outline

1. Indoor accelerated testing

2. PID in outdoor conditions

Experimental tests

Mathematical model for PID indoors at constant stress conditions:

- **Equations (deg & reg)**
 $P(t) = P(t, T, RH, V)$
- **Parameters** (E_a, λ, \dots)
(specific to module type)

Simulations

(*) Matlab PV_LIB toolbox (Sandia Laboratories) + Typical Metereological Year data

PID degradation/regeneration cycles during day/night (1)

Thresholds on weather data

Deeper understanding is still needed for:

- Alternating **degradation/regeneration cycles** during **daytime**
- **Module surface** being **wet or dry**

PID degradation/regeneration cycles during day/night (2)

Thresholds on weather data

Deeper understanding is still needed for:

- Alternating **degradation/regeneration cycles** during **daytime**
- Module surface being wet or dry

We arbitrarily set some thresholds on meteo data to model degradation/regeneration

PID degradation/regeneration cycles during day/night (3)

Thresholds on weather data

Better comprehension still needed for:

- Degradation/regeneration alternation during daytime
- Module surface being wet or dry

We arbitrarily set some thresholds on meteo data to model degradation/regeneration.

Simulation results – Different climates

- Suppose **mini-module** installed in four locations (four different climates)
- Assume constant $V = -1000$ V during daytime

- **Cyclic behavior** \Leftarrow seasonal alternation of degr./regeneration
- Maximum extent of degradation in **hot and humid** climate

Simulation results

Comparison with field experience

Our simulations on mini-modules
(Miami)

Measurements on commercial modules
(Florida)

Conclusions

- Our simulations **able to reproduce** same **seasonal trend** observed in Florida.
- Different levels of power loss reflect different performance in laboratory testing (not shown here).

Simulation results – PID at string level

Module position
in the string

Voltage against
ground

PID
degradation

- So far: 2-cell mini-modules,
fixed voltage $V = -1000$ V.

- Here: **commercial 60-cell modules**
- String of 34 modules
- **PID stress voltage** at each time t_i :

$$V_{mpp}(i, j) = V_{mpp}(t_i) \cdot j$$

Real instant voltage of module in
position j

- Linear behavior observed in PV plants is reproduced.
- We can simulate the performance of the string at any given time.

Conclusions

➔ More realistic simulations of PID in **real outdoors conditions**

- Improvements with respect to state-of-the-art:
 - Dependence on V modeled \Rightarrow simulations at **string** level
 - **Daytime regeneration** (negative voltage) modeled
 - More accurate use of **meteorological data** (daytime deg./reg., wet/dry module surface)
- Currently attempting a **validation**
 - First trial with commercial modules no good results (different bill of materials)
- Include irradiance as (mitigating) factor for degradation?

Accelerated test matrix for modelling PID

- PID test matrix to extract module parameters for performance prediction in a given location

Degradation

T / RH	75%	85%	95%
60°C	-1000 V	-1000 V	-1000 V
85°C	/	-1000 V -500 V	/

Duration each condition: 192h (at least)
Performance characterization every 96h

Regeneration

Dark tests
Duration: 1000 h
Charact. every 100 h

Illumination tests
Duration: 700 h
Charact. every 100 h

Nighttime (dark)		Daytime (illumination)			
Load condition	T [°C]	T [°C]	Irradiance [W/m ²]	Voltage [V]	Degradation level P _{min} /P _{ini} [%]
OC (no voltage)	20	60	1000	-600 V	10
	60				30
	85				50
					70

Thank you for your attention!

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Swiss Confederation

Commission for Technology and Innovation CTI

Supplementary material

PID cycles and recovery capacity

Recovery capacity # of “PID cycles” [Koch]

- 1 PID cycle := 1 day
- We integrate a “**dampening factor**” (DF) that depends on the # of PID cycles.
- DF values hypothetical. Accelerated tests required to determine them.

Regeneration under irradiance: impact of irradiance

- Effect of irradiance level not very pronounced
- Damage level plays a role.

Power regeneration: impact of temperature

- Effect of temperature not very evident
- Testing at wider range of temperatures might provide further information.

Input meteorological data

- **Typical meteorological year (TMY) data**
- Time-resolution: 1h
- Source: Meteonorm

Module instantaneous nominal power P_{nom}

- P_{nom} of the mini-module is calculated with hourly resolution over the time period of interest (e.g. 25 years)

PID phases - Module surface wet or dry

Module temperature

- **King's** equation overestimates temperature at night
- **Myers/Kempe** model takes into account module **cooling** due to **radiative heat transfer to the sky**

Conclusion

- We propose a method to estimate T_{mod} **more suitable** for modeling PID:
 - King's model: daytime
 - Kempe's model: nighttime

Simulation results

Comparison with field experience

Our simulations on mini-modules
(Miami)

60°C / 85% RH / -1000 V (96h)
 $\Delta P = -1.5\%$

Measurements on commercial modules
(Florida)

60°C / 85% RH / -600 V (40h)
 $\Delta P = -50\%$

Lab testing
Conclusions

- Our simulations **able to reproduce** same **seasonal trend** observed in Florida.
- Different levels of power loss reflect different performance in laboratory testing.